

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 120

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 120

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 120:0 A Song of †Ascents.</p>	
<p>Psa. 120:1 "In my trouble I cried to the LORD, And He answered me. ² Deliver my soul, O LORD, from ^alying lips, From a ^bdeceitful tongue. ³ What shall be given to you, and what more shall be done to you, You ^adeceitful tongue? ⁴ "Sharp arrows of the warrior, With the <i>burning</i> ^bcoals of the broom tree.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 120:1</p> <p style="text-align: right;">שִׁיר הַמַּעֲלֹת אֶל־יְהוָה בִּצְרָתָהּ לִי קָרָאתִי וַיַּעֲנֵנִי : ² יְהוָה הֲצִילָה נַפְשִׁי מִשִּׁפְּת־שָׁקֶר מִלְּשׁוֹן רְמִיָּה : ³ מַה־יִּתֵּן לָךְ וּמַה־יִּסְיֶךָ לָךְ לְשׁוֹן רְמִיָּה : ⁴ חֲצֵי גִבּוֹר שְׁנוּנִים עִם גִּחְלֵי רִתְּמִים : ⁵ אֹיְהָ־ לִי כִי־גִרְתִּי מִשָּׂדֶךְ שְׁכֻנָּתִי עִם־ אֶחְלֵי קֶדָר : ⁶ רַבַּת שְׁכֻנָּה־לָּהּ נַפְשִׁי עִם שׁוֹנֵא שָׁלוֹם : ⁷ אֲנִי־שָׁלוֹם וְכִי אֲדַבֵּר הִנֵּה לְמַלְחָמָה :</p>
<p>Psa. 120:5 Woe is me, for I sojourn in ^aMeshech, For I dwell among the ^btents of ^aKedar! ⁶ Too long has my soul had its dwelling With those who ^ahate peace. ⁷ I ^aam <i>for</i> peace, but when I speak, They are ^bfor war.</p>	

References

Psalm 120:0

[†]Ex 34:24; 1 Kin 12:27

Psalm 120:1

^aPs 18:6; 66:14; 102:2; Jon 2:2

Psalm 120:2

^aPs 109:2; Prov 12:22

^bPs 52:4; Zeph 3:13

Psalm 120:3

^aPs 52:4; Zeph 3:13

Psalm 120:4

^aPs 45:5; Prov 25:18; Is 5:28

^bPs 140:10

Psalm 120:5

^aGen 10:2; 1 Chr 1:5; Ezek 27:13; 38:2, 3; 39:1

^bSong 1:5

^cGen 25:13; Is 21:16; 60:7; Jer 2:10; 49:28; Ezek 27:21

Psalm 120:6

^aPs 35:20

Psalm 120:7

^aPs 109:4

^bPs 55:21

Targum

Psa. 120:1 A song that was uttered on the ascents of the abyss. In the presence of the LORD, when I was in distress, I prayed, and he received my prayer. ² O LORD, deliver my soul from lips of deceit, from a deceptive tongue. ³ What does he give to you, O slanderer? And what does he add to you, O defamer, deceptive tongue? ⁴ The arrows of a warrior, sharp as lightning from above, with coals of broom that burn in Gehenna below. ⁵ Woe is me, for I have settled down with the oasis-dwellers; I have dwelt with the tents of the Arabs. ⁶ More than these, my soul abides with Edom, the hater of peace. ⁷ I am peaceful, for I will pray; [but] they are for war.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The next fifteen psalms describe the rising fortunes of wise persons. They are called a Song of Ascents because the Children of Israel are worthy to ascend. They do not climb one rung at a time, but numerous rungs at a time. However, if Israel cannot follow the LORD, they will descend many levels as once (Deuteronomy 28:43). They sang these fifteen Psalms in the Temple because they believed that Israel's ascent would occur in that location.

Verse five

Meshech was a son of Japheth, son of Noah. Kedar was a son of Ishmael. These people were Bedouins. The Psalmist says that if evil overtook him, it would be equivalent to living like a Bedouin. These people did not have a permanent place to live. They moved from location to location in the desert. It is best to do good and live according to the words of the LORD. By living in this manner, one will have a permanent place to spiritually live. It also can refer to the next world. Upon death, a righteous person has better options than a sinful person.

O would that I had sojourned among Meshech, that I dwelt besides the tents of Kedar.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

